

A Study of Student Enrollment of Foreign Students for Post Graduate and Doctoral Degree in Indian Universities, Institutes and Colleges

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ABSTRACT

This study is an effort to understand the admission of students from foreign nations for the post graduate and doctoral degree. A gender wise and course wise analysis is undertaken in order to compare the trends in admission 2011-2017. An effort has been taken to understand the various reasons for the increase or decrease in the number of foreign students for the courses.

Keywords: Rights, Acts, P.hD, M.Phil, AISHE, ICCR, Ministry of External Affairs

INTRODUCTION

India has always been an education hub. The formal education in India was set up in the British era and since then there has been tremendous changes and modification in the education system in India. The main mode of education language in India is English which was introduced by the British India. English being a globally accepted language has enabled us to establish great institutes and universities in various fields such as medicine, technology, commerce, management and other general courses.

These institutes offering a wide variety of courses for acquiring knowledge and the English medium of education in India has attracted lot of admission from foreign nationals. Admission of foreign students in Indian students first received a boost in the year 1950 when The Indian Council for Cultural Relations was established under the guidance of Hon. Maulana Abdul Kalam Azad who was the first Education Minister of Independent India. The main objective of

establishing ICCR was to inculcate and grow India's External Cultural Relations and to strengthen mutual relationship between Indian and other countries by cultural exchanges with foreign countries. ICCR also offered scholarships to foreign students who wanted to pursue higher studies in Indian Universities. In the year 2016-17 approximately Ninety Five thousand foreign students are enrolled in various certificates, integrated, graduate, post graduate, M.Phil, Ph.D and other programs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Objective of Study: The main objective of studying this topic is study the enrolment scenario of foreign students for research studies and post graduate studies in India and the gender wise enrolment in Ph.D and M.Phil degree

Scope of Study: This study can help us to understand the impact of culture, various norms and regulation of universities and governing bodies in the admission of foreign students.

Methodology Used: Secondary based research has been done and data for analysis has been collected from published reports of UGS, AISHE and Government of India.

Limitation of study: This research is based on descriptive case study method of research based on secondary data. This study is limited to data collected for the year 2013-17

DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Foreign Students Studying in Indian Universities/Colleges/Institutes										
	No. of students									
	2010-11		2013-14		2014-15		2015-16		2016-17	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female
PH.D	583	249	730	208	876	290	883	288	1202	321
M.PHIL	56	51	39	25	38	35	37	22	53	29
POST GRAD	3812	1646	4591	1847	4654	1932	4530	1895	4871	2041
TOTAL	4451	1946	5360	2080	5568	2257	5450	2205	6126	2391

Source: AISHE Reports

Tab 1: Foreign students enrolled in Indian Universities/colleges/institutes 2011-2017. The above table shows the cumulative and gender wise enrollment of foreign students in Ph.D, M.Phil and Post Graduate Studies for the year 2011-2017.

Graph 1: Gender wise enrollment of foreign students in Indian Universities/Colleges/Institutes 2011-17

The above graph shows a comparative status gender-wise of year 2010-2011 and 2016-17. The graph denotes the increase/decrease in enrollment status of foreign students for research and post graduate studies in Indian Universities/Colleges/Institutes.

Findings1: The graph shows that there has been a steady increase in enrollment of both male and female students for Ph.D and post graduate courses/degree. Since the year 2010-11 there has been approximately 58% increase in the enrollment of students in Ph.d degree and 27% increase in the enrollment of students in Post Graduate Degree. *This shows that there is an increase in preference of the foreign students to approach Indian Universities / Colleges/Institute for Doctoral Degree Program. However there has been*

a negative growth in the preference of M.Phil program by foreign students.

Findings 2: The graph shows the comparative enrollment of male and female students. On further analysis it is found out that there is a small growth of 29% in preference of female foreign student for Doctoral Degree since 2010-11 but almost 100% growth in preference of male foreign students for Doctoral Degree. *This shows that there has been a positive increase in the number of male foreign students registered for Doctoral Degree i.e. P.hD degree since 2010-11*

Finding 3: The graph shows the comparative enrollment of male and female students. On further analysis it is found out that there is a growth of 24%

in preference of female foreign student for Post Graduate Degree

Since 2010-11 and 28% growth in preference of male foreign students for Post Graduate Degree. *This shows that there has been only a marginal increase in the enrollment of male and female students for the Post Graduate Degree since 2010-11.*

Finding 4: The graph shows the comparative enrollment of male and female students. On further analysis it is found out that there is a negative growth of 43% in preference of female foreign student for M.Phil degree.

Since 2010-11 and a negative growth of 5% in preference of male foreign students for Post Graduate Degree. *This shows that fewer and fewer foreign students are interested in enrolling for the M.Phil degree, but the percentage of foreign female students NOT OPTING for this degree has increased since 2010-11.*

SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

There has been an increase in the enrollment of foreign students since 2010-11 especially for Doctoral Degree Program. However considering the International Scenario of Education the number of foreign students enrolled in India is only 0.61% which is abysmal if compared with USA, UK and Australia. The low admission status of foreign as compared to the global scenario can be attributed to certain specific reasons.

Firstly there is a very low marketing or promotion of Indian Education in the international market. Many of the global students are not aware of the educational opportunities in India. Secondly the cultural difference especially for African and European students and inability of the Indian society to accept these students socially makes it very difficult for the students to pursue their education in India. There have been reports of assaults on foreign students in India. Thereby more and more African and European students are not willing to pursue education in India. Thirdly the rigors of registration for admission of foreign students. Foreign students have to undergo rigorous registration formalities which include securing the student visa, foreign travel protocols, and registration formalities. Apart from registering at the FRRO (Foreign Regional Registration Office) foreign the students as per rules also have to register with wither one of the three bodies i.e. Association of

University, Ministry of External Affairs and Indian Council for Cultural Relations and get their documents attested from any one of these three bodies.

On the basis of the analysis and findings it can be aptly suggested there is an urgent need for Indian Universities/Colleges/Institutes along with Government of India various ministries and bodies to strengthen the branding of Indian Education at the global level. This can increase the access of desirable foreign students to information regarding the education system, admission procedure and various courses.

It is also noted that the tuition fees for foreign students are at a higher side normally the acceptable foreign currency in terms of Dollars. This can be a drawback for foreign students from lesser developing nations such as Rwanda or Somalia etc. Hence a separate fee structure should be framed for students coming from lesser developing nations.

Accommodation and staying facilities should be adequately maintained and should be provided at lower costs for foreign students. Separate, Affordable and Secure Staying and transportation facilities should be made for Female Foreign Students should be given priority.

Indian localities should be educated in terms of acceptance of these students in the society and to avoid any racial discrimination and conflicts.

The administration and registration process initiated by the Immigration Department, Government Bodies, Universities and Institutes should be streamlined and a separate individual department totally dedicated to the foreign students should be formed in order to simply the procedure.

Periodic upgradation of the courses according to the changing global scenario and requirements should be done. Special emphasis to modify the M.Phil Degree should be undertaken in order to attract more foreign students. Information regarding the courses, its module and fees should be easily accessible to the students. There is also a need to increase the quota of foreign students in India from the current quota of 15%

On the conclusion it can be concluded that there is an urgent need to identify the potential of making India an education hub for foreign students. This can also increase the inflow of foreign currency in India and thus contribute to the economy of India. There is a further scope of this study and an in-depth and detailed research should be undertaken in this area.

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